

A Case of Oesophageal Stenting with Simultaneous Percutaneous Endoscopic Gastrostomy for Supplementary Feeding in a Patient with Oesophageal Carcinoma

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ABSTRACT: Patients with carcinoma oesophagus often suffer from nutritional deprivation and poor quality life as well as aspiration pneumonia, as a consequence of malignant oesophageal stricture. There are several palliative interventions to overcome such issues. The more recent, but perhaps the

most effective one probably is simultaneous implantation of self-expandable mesh-metallic stent into oesophagus and percutaneous endoscopic gastrostomy performed at upper gastro-intestinal tract endoscopy under anesthesia. Here, we report the first such case from Bangladesh.

Keywords: *Oesophageal carcinoma, malignant stricture, self-expandable mesh-metallic stent, percutaneous endoscopic gastrostomy*

Introduction

Patients with oesophageal carcinoma suffer from a wide range of complications, namely, oesophago-tracheal fistula, choking with food and/or saliva, repeated aspiration pneumonia, vocal cord paralysis, rapid weight loss etc., which in turn contribute to poor quality of life and to poorer prognosis.

There are different modalities of palliative treatment for oesophageal carcinoma patients. These include oesophageal stenting, feeding gastrostomy or jejunostomy, chemotherapy and/or radiotherapy and laser or photodynamic intraluminal therapy. Such treatment is indicated for relapsed oesophageal carcinoma as well as inoperative cases in order to restore oesophageal patency to allow feeding thus improving nutritional status and quality of life [1].

However, these procedures may be hazardous. Gastrostomy and/or jejunostomy and adjuvant chemotherapy and/or radiotherapy are the procedures that are usually employed in order to manage such patients. However, complications like dysphagia, aspiration of food and/or saliva remain unresolved despite these approaches.

Case Report

The patient was an elderly lady over 70 years of age, who presented with dysphagia with inability to swallow semi-solid food and weight loss. Among other investigations, she underwent an upper gastrointestinal tract (UGIT) endoscopy, which revealed a growth in the upper oesophagus approximately 30 cm from the lower incisor teeth occluding oesophageal lumen. Biopsies were taken from the growth at endoscopy and sent for histopathology, which established the diagnosis of squamous cell carcinoma oesophageal carcinoma.

According to a four-grade scale, she had grade 3 dysphagia i.e. inability to swallow liquids and saliva [2]. We decided to place an oesophageal stent at endoscopy of UGIT. Location of the growth and its distance from the lower incisor teeth was reconfirmed endoscopically. Oesophageal dilatation was then done at endoscopy of UGIT with Savary-Gilliard dilators (10-14 Fr) over guidewire. After dilatation, length of the stricture was determined at endoscopy of UGIT. A 12 cm long partially covered self-expandable metallic stent (SEMS) (Boston Scientific, Natick, USA) was then deployed in the oesophageal lumen over guidewire across the growth at endoscopy of UGIT. The stent was positioned to cover 2-4 cm of the oesophageal wall above and below the growth. The procedure was performed under total intravenous anesthesia (TIVA) with injection propofol 1.5 to 2 mg/kg body weight. She was followed up on the day following the procedure and then at 1-monthly intervals. During follow up, among other things, dysphagia and quality of life were carefully assessed.

The patient developed complaints of recurrence of dysphagia, repeated vomiting and respiratory distress 5 months after SEMS placement. She also experienced rapid weight loss. Investigations revealed that she had developed aspiration pneumonia. Repeat endoscopy of UGIT revealed, stent obstruction by granulation tissue overgrowth, which is not infrequent in such patients, seen in up to 13% patients with implanted SEMS in situ [3, 4].

After she improved with conservative treatment, repeat oesophageal dilatation was done at endoscopy of UGIT over guidewire using Savary-Gilliard dilators (10-14 Fr) and subsequently a second SEMS was introduced into the oesophagus within the SEMS in situ over guidewire covering the tissue overgrowth (Figure-1 & 2). Although technically challenging, additional 'telescopic SEMS-in-SEMS' introduction is practiced in such cases [5]. A percutaneous endoscopic gastrostomy (PEG) tube was then introduced into the stomach across the SEMS-in-SEMS in situ endoscopically using 'pull technique' [6]. The patient was followed up following the same schedule.

Discussion

Patients with malignant oesophageal stricture, especially involving the upper third, are at risk of developing vocal cord paralysis, oesophago-tracheal fistula, rapid weight loss, aspiration pneumonia resulting from aspiration of saliva and ingested food, disability and poor quality of life. Feeding gastrostomy or jejunostomy and adjuvant radiotherapy and chemotherapy remain the frequently employed palliative interventions for such patients. However, these measures do not resolve the risk of aspiration pneumonia. Moreover, such measures are frequently associated with anxiety and depression [5].

Oesophageal stents can be successfully deployed in 73-100% cases by experienced Endoscopists restoring oesophageal patency, thus allowing normal food intake [7, 8]. They also resolve the issue of oesophago-tracheal fistula, which complicate oesophageal cancers in 0.9-18% cases [9]. It is a relatively safe procedure with 0-5% mortality [3]. However, oesophageal SEMSs come with several limitations. Complications are seen in up to 34% cases and include stent migration and discomfort and impaired swallowing, especially with SEMS implanted close to the upper oesophageal sphincter, and compromised quality of life [10, 11, 12, 3].

SEMS is preferred over self-expandable plastic stents (SEPS), as they migrate less frequently, even during simultaneous PEG introduction using the 'pull technique', when the bumper of PEG catheter is pulled through the SEMS in situ.

Most importantly, even after oesophageal patency is restored, nutritional requirements cannot always be met. Simultaneous PEG and oesophageal stenting can resolve this issue, as adequate nutrition can then be supplied through the supplementary enteral feeding route [13, 14]. It has been experienced that 60-80% of patients with oesophageal cancers are undernourished [15, 16]. Following, simultaneous SEMS implantation and PEG, mean drop of body weight reduces from 11.35 kg to 3.75 kg in such patients [17, 18].

A Polish study involving 45 oesophageal carcinoma patients who underwent simultaneous SEMS implantation and PEG, 73.3% were able to swallow semi-solid food, while 24.4% patients could only take liquid ones post-procedure [5].

Dysphagia improved and mean body-weight loss 6-months post-procedure improved from -10.1 kg to +2 kg. Besides, performance status of the patients were also improved. None of the patients included in the study experienced any serious adverse event. Complications included neck discomfort (37.7%), foreign body sensation in oesophagus (4.4%) etc. to name a few.

Conclusion

Simultaneous SEMS implantation and PEG is a safe procedure. The advantages that this endoscopic intervention offers, far outweighs the handful of occasional adverse events associated with it. Although this is not indicated for all patients of malignant oesophageal structure, it should be actively considered when weight loss becomes an issue, despite successful deployment of SEMS.

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Figure-1: Introduction of PEG catheter through MESH in MESH in situ at endoscopy of UGIT by pull technique

Figure-2: Introduction of PEG catheter through MESH in MESH in situ at endoscopy of UGIT by pull technique